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Climb to Mt. Matunog

Rain turned the trail to mud,
my pack was heavy,
my steps are uncertain.

I slipped,
fell,

rose again.

The mountain tested me,
but I kept moving
and at the summit

I found the lesson:

You only see the beauty
if you endure the climb.